

Deliverable 4.1

*Outcomes of the regional co-creation process
and pilot selection*

TRANSFORM

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Summary.

This deliverable presents the outcomes of the regional co-creation process and pilot selection in the Catalan region. This process was undertaken by the Catalan cluster, which is composed of Science for Change, Catalan Government, and OpenSystemsUB. The cluster is experimenting with public engagement and citizen science in Catalonia, intending to better understand how such approaches might contribute and inform public policies. In this sense, this deliverable aims to document and illustrate the regional co-creation process, which led to the co-design and selection of the regional pilots' projects.

Chapter 1. Introduces the contextualization of the deliverable.

Chapter 2. Documents the process to select the main topic to develop citizen science pilots in Catalonia.

Chapter 3. Presents the process of co-designing the pilots with the main stakeholders.

Chapter 4. Next activities to be carried out.

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1. Introduction

In TRANSFORM, three European regions work together to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation (RRI).

The RRI actions under TRANSFORM focus on public engagement and governance with the aim of contributing to the common good by aligning the development of science and technology with the values, needs and concerns of society through the regional smart specialisation strategies.

Lombardy in Italy, Brussels in Belgium and Catalonia in Spain are all leaders in experimenting with new pathways for territorial development. TRANSFORM brings them together to design, test and disseminate three sound co-creation methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting in Lombardy; design thinking for social innovation in Brussels; and public engagement and citizen science in Catalonia). Regional governments involved in TRANSFORM are able to reflect on, experiment with and learn from this approach.

In Catalonia, the TRANSFORM cluster is composed of Science for Change, an SME specialised in citizen science, co-creation and participatory strategies, which acts as cluster leader; the Catalan Government (General Directorate for Economic Promotion, Competition and Regulation), in charge of planning the Smart Specialisation Strategy in Catalonia (called RIS3CAT); and OpenSystemsUB, a research group at the University of Barcelona with broad expertise in citizen science.

The Catalan Cluster is particularly interested in exploring the potential of citizen science (CS) to co-design and implement public policies that are more effective in addressing the challenges that matter to society. Particularly:

- The potential of CS to improve understanding and management of sustainability transitions;
- The potential of CS to reveal the blind spots in current public action(s) or solution(s) that can lead to the inability to change their current pathway or to unintentional side effects;
- The potential of CS as a tool to engage citizens in policy-making and public services co-design processes, improving their performance.

TRANSFORM offers an experimentation space that allows Catalan stakeholders to explore how CS could be integrated into Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3CAT). CS challenges the

separation of science from society and, therefore, is a powerful tool to articulate new forms of collaboration between academia, public administrations, companies and civil society to address more effectively the challenges that matter to society.

This deliverable describes the regional co-creation process undertaken by the Catalan Cluster to design and select the two TRANSFORM citizen science pilot projects. The co-creation process was structured in two phases.

Phase 1. Creation of a discussion forum to develop a common understanding on the potential of citizen science to inform public policies and to identify potential pilot projects within the RIS3CAT framework. To this end, the Catalan Cluster articulated a Think Tank with stakeholders from the Catalan research and innovation ecosystem (mainly public administrations, universities and companies). The main result of the four Think Tank sessions organised in 2020 was the identification of the themes and the main stakeholders for the development of the two pilot projects.

Phase 2. Selection and design of the two pilot projects, in collaboration with the main stakeholders.

2. Selection of the topics within the TRANSFORM Think Tank

The Think Tank was conceived as an expert group to support the mapping, reflection process and action development of the TRANSFORM project in Catalonia. The main objectives of the Think Tank were defined as follows:

- 1) To contribute to the assessment of the state of RRI and public participation in the R&I ecosystem in Catalonia.
- 2) To inform public agendas and strategies.
- 3) To participate in capacity building sessions.
- 4) To contribute to defining collaborative propositions on how to improve the openness and inclusiveness of the regional R&I ecosystem.
- 5) To reflect on and learn from the pilot projects to be developed in Catalonia.

The Catalan Think Tank was launched in June 2020 with participation of more than 55 members from the Catalan R&I ecosystem (see deliverable 2.1 List of Think Tank members). The Think Tank is composed of policy makers from the regional government, policy makers from local administrations (mostly working on environmental issues), researchers from universities and research centres, and companies and entities providing public services (in waste management, water supply and health).

From June to December 2020, the Catalan Cluster organised 4 participatory capacity building sessions on RRI and Citizen Science (CS) for the members of the Think Tank. These sessions were an opportunity to exchange perspectives and views on the role and potential of CS to inform public policies more aligned with societal needs. One of the main topics discussed was how CS can contribute to articulating new forms of collaboration among academia, public administrations, companies and civil society to address the challenges that matter to society more effectively. The webinars were an opportunity for exploring how public administrations and researchers could work together to address more effectively the challenges that matter to society. These webinars were conceived as a process of learning and reflection ranging from the most abstract concepts to their practical application and action. The exercises proposed in the webinars allowed the Catalan Cluster, after intense reflection on RRI and CS, to identify the topics and main stakeholders for the two pilot projects.

In the following sections we describe the main learnings from the 4 sessions that finally allowed the Catalan Cluster to identify the most interesting CS pilots with a view to ensuring the widest possible impact on RIS3.

Title	Date	N. of attendees	Objectives	Outputs
What can RRI & citizen science do for you?	Jul. 21, 2020	64	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To establish a common knowledge on RRI and CS 2. To promote mutual understanding among participants 3. To begin to identify possible ways of applying citizen science as a tool for incorporating RRI dimensions in R&I public policies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Surveys on knowledge and opinions about RRI dimensions & CS ● RRI dimensions prioritisation (by sectoral area) ● Qualitative opinions about RRI aspects that should be addressed
Potential of citizen science to address social and environmental issues, increasing the impact of public policies	Sept. 21, 2020	52	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To reflect on the potential of citizen-generated data to inform public policies 2. To identify interesting data sets that could be generated by citizens 3. To identify enabling conditions in a collaboration framework of 4H agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● List of possible data sets generated by citizens (by sectoral area) ● List of roles of the different stakeholders in developing CS projects (by sectoral area) ● List of enabling conditions for citizen-generated data ● List of enabling conditions for citizen-generated data to actually inform public policy
How to start co-designing a citizen science project to address a socio-environmental challenge (I)	Nov. 20, 2020	46	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To start co-designing a CS project, defining objectives and addressing RRI dimensions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Real socio-environmental challenges in the fields of health, waste and water. ● Objectives and RRI dimensions to address for each challenge

<p>How to start co-designing a citizen science project to address a socio-environmental challenge (II)</p>	<p>Dec. 4, 2020</p>	<p>48</p>	<p>1. To start co-designing a CS project, defining the scope, data to be collected, and citizens to be engaged</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope of the projects • Citizen generated data to be generated • Citizens to be engaged and engagement strategies
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Table 1. Summary of the 4 participatory capacity building sessions

2.1 Webinar 1: What can RRI and CS do for you?

Development of the session

<p>1. RRI and citizen science in the institutions:</p>	<p>Explanation of the concept and dimensions of RRI, based on practical examples and their possible applications. Presentation of citizen science as a tool for in-depth citizen participation with the potential to increase the impact of research and innovation policies and projects. During the presentation, surveys were conducted to collect the participants' opinions as regards various key aspects of RRI.</p>
<p>2. Debate on RRI with practical examples of citizen science:</p>	<p>Division of the participants into 4 groups (Environmental quality, Water, Health, and Waste) and presentation of 3-4 citizen science projects related to the group's particular theme. Discussion of different aspects of RRI that can be developed through citizen science, and prioritisation of RRI dimensions in each group.</p>

Table 2. Thematic structure of the first webinar

Results of surveys

Image 1. Results on gender survey (Catalan)

As regards gender, the overall conclusion is that, while practices with gender perspective proposed receive considerable support, none are applied at more than 55% of organisations. 75% of the

participants state that an equality plan has been introduced at their organisations; of this percentage, 70% consider that plans are implemented correctly, while 30% consider that their provisions are not applied (52% and 23% of the total respectively). Moreover, only just over 50% of participants state that they include the sex/gender perspective in their research, policies, calls for proposals, etc. Finally, less than 50% (42%) of participants report that inclusive language and images are used at their organisations.

Image 2. Results on public participation survey (Catalan)

As regards citizen participation, a large majority (84%) consider it vital to include this aspect in research and innovation processes in order to align science with society. On the other hand, 14% consider it important to take into account the opinions of citizens but not necessarily to include them in research and innovation processes.

Image 3. Results on ethics survey (Catalan)

As regards ethics, there are three ethical aspects that a large majority consider relevant to their professional practice. These are: protection of personal and/or sensitive data (94%); transparency in recruitment processes (81%); and informed consent (79%). Around 50% mention not raising false

expectations (57%) and ethical practices in research with humans (it should be noted that not all the organisations engage in this type of research).

Image 4. Results on open access survey (Catalan)

As regards open access to research and publication data, 86% consider this totally necessary, but of this total, the 45% feel that traceability of the authorship should be guaranteed (39% of the total) and 38% that intellectual property rights should be guaranteed (33% of the total). Finally, 10% consider that openness to data and publications is not necessary, whether to guarantee the right to competition or for other reasons.

Image 5. Results on open access survey (Catalan)

As regards the governance dimension, the survey shows that nearly half the participants (45%) consider that a basic grounding in science is not a requirement for taking part in decision-making. On the other hand, the same percentage (42%) believe that current levels of scientific knowledge are very

low and generate little informed decision-making, and that citizens do not have enough critical thinking. Only 4% believe that it is science that should define the priorities of research and innovation.

Image 6. Results on education in science survey (Catalan)

As regards the dimension of education in science, more than a third of attendees believe that participatory activities are the best tools to educate in this subject, followed very closely by 35% who believe the best way is through citizen science. 18% consider museums and new digital formats to be the best tool, while 10% do not identify with any of the above statements. One of the participants openly stated that their conviction that science education requires a combination of tools and that one or another might be more effective depending on the specific situation and audience.

Image 7. Results on education in science survey (Catalan)

Finally, as regards citizen science, 40% of the participants consider this the best methodology to align science with society, followed by 1/3 who consider it important because it enables the generation of mass data sets. On the other hand, nearly 25% see citizen science as a complement but not a substitute for traditional research, while 4% express an interest in involving citizens only as "sensors".

Results from the prioritisation of the different aspects of RRI

It is observed that, in all groups, none of the dimensions receives less than 3 points out of 5. This indicates that all the dimensions of RRI are relevant according to the participants. Generally speaking, citizen participation is the most highly rated dimension, receiving almost 5 points from all groups. Education in science (Environmental Quality), governance (Environmental Quality and Waste) and open access (Health) received the same score. In the Environmental Quality group, open access received a score of 4 and ethics had a score of 3.5. In the Waste group, education in science, open access and ethics were all ranked equally in importance, receive, 4 points each. Science, ethics and governance also received 4 points in the Health group. In the Water group, education in science, governance and open access were given 4 points. Generally speaking, gender and ethics are the least highly valued dimensions (gender receiving between 3 and 3.5 points; ethics, between 3 and 4 points).

Results from the debate on RRI and citizen science

Below are the replies received to the question “what specific aspects do you think are or should be implemented as part of RRI?”

<p>Citizen participation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generate mass data to reach more territories ● Broaden participation: participatory activities can be conducted from the data and/or opinion collecting phase to the design and evaluation phase ● Include and empower minorities and unmotivated people ● Develop living labs, pilots, etc., in order to move into action ● Involve patients as health research stakeholders ● Emphasise the capacity for participation of elderly people
<p>Education in science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reach families through students ● Review formal curricula and provide both non-formal and informal channels for education in science ● Establish contact with other sectors, through science education, art or other means ● Place the child at the centre, raising awareness and empowering them from an early age ● Promote critical thinking and empowerment ● Involve secondary school students in data collection and processing
<p>Governance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Citizen science enables data collection and the involvement of many citizens ● Stress the importance of think tanks

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highlight the role of living labs ● Important to take into consideration and adopt initiatives launched by citizens ● Increase the participation of citizens in the governing bodies of institutions ● Respond to challenges identified in citizen participation through public policies
Open data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote the provision and sharing of data among organisations: it is a challenge to generate homogeneous or comparable data ● Generate open data platforms for both the scientific community and the population as a whole ● Collect individualised data in order to design systems better: prioritise the return of results to the public ● Raise awareness through the use of data
Research ethics and integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote data sovereignty: data belongs to citizens/users ● Focus on initiatives as a common good and not an individual good ● Include the anthropological perspective: the approach behind initiatives should take into account differences in perceptions among different social stakeholders ● Include clear, understandable and inclusive data protection and informed consent policies ● Promote more ethical behaviour among citizens
Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guarantee equality between men and women in samples in clinical studies, and study gender as a singular variable ● Take the gender perspective into account in working and research conditions ● Send out communication messages that do not reproduce or reinforce certain stereotypes

Table 3. Participants' opinions about RRI and CS

General conclusions from the session

This first session was used to launch the Think Tank and to open up a debate on citizen science among various stakeholders in the research and innovation ecosystem of Catalonia. The session served mainly to start constructing a common basis from which researchers and public policy managers can jointly explore and study how citizen science and its methodologies and tools can help to improve the quality and effectiveness of public actions or, in the case of companies and other entities, their products and services), and respond to societal challenges (in the areas of the environment, social inclusion, public health, etc.). One of the challenges of the Think Tank is to enable the visions and language of researchers and the managers of public policies or services together and to promote new dynamics of collaboration to more effectively address the societal challenges, that is, those challenges that most concern citizens.

At the session, the main concepts of RRI and citizen science were explained through practical examples, highlighting the value that citizen science can bring to R&I projects and public policies. Organisations with experience in citizen science described their areas of activity and their main projects. This is very important, as the Think Tank should help to articulate a network of different stakeholders who understand the potential of incorporating the approach, methodologies and tools of citizen science into the design of public policies and services and which cooperate to implement citizen science.

It became clear at the session that there is great interest (on the part of public administrations, companies that provide services and researchers) in involving citizens in research and innovation projects and in the design of public policies and services.

2.2 Webinar 2: Potential of citizen science to address social and environmental challenges, enhancing the impact of public policies

Development of the session

<p>1. Presentation of the 1st part. Potential of citizen science: data generation</p>	<p>Explanation of the advantages of data generated by citizens compared to data generated in traditional ways. Explanation of the different procedures for collecting data through citizen science.</p>
<p>2. Exercise 1. Data generated by citizens with the potential to address socio-environmental challenges</p>	<p>Division of the participants into four groups (Environmental Quality, Water, Health, and Waste) according to the choice made previously. Identification of the most important socio-environmental challenges in their respective fields. Reflection on how data generated by citizens could contribute to meeting challenges. Reflection on the contribution that each quadruple helix player should make to enable citizen science projects to be developed and address these challenges.</p>
<p>3. Presentation of the 2nd part. Potential of citizen science: informing public policies</p>	<p>Explanation of how citizen-generated data can contribute to various phases of the public policy-making cycle, highlighting the EU's interest in the subject and the potential contribution of such data to monitoring SDGs, particularly at the local and regional level.</p>
<p>4. Exercise 2. What are the necessary conditions for the data generated by citizens to contribute to informing public policies?</p>	<p>Division of the participants into the same four thematic groups. Reflection on how, specifically, citizen-generated data can inform public policies, focusing on the conditions necessary for this contribution to become effective.</p>

Table 4. Thematic structure of the second webinar

Results from the session

Thematic group on Water

Question 1: What are the most important socio-environmental challenges in the field of water

The participants identified four challenges. Two of them (challenges 1 and 3) are related to the state of water and aquatic systems, and the other two (challenges 2 and 4) are related to the changes necessary in citizens' behaviour and perception. The four challenges are: water pollution/quality; responsible consumption; regeneration of riparian forests/aquatic systems; and public perceptions of aquatic spaces/systems.

Question 2: How can data sets generated through citizen science help to inform or improve public policies?

Most of the responses focused on Challenge 1, water pollution. According to the participants, citizen science could help to provide real-time data on a wide range of indicators, to identify sources of pollution and to conduct biological and macroscopic monitoring in different urban and rural areas. Moreover, knowledge of the uses that citizens make of aquatic spaces could be useful for designing better conservation policies.

Regarding Challenge 1, water pollution, attendees noted that data could be useful in identifying and locating sources of pollution and improving the water quality of sources at regional level. Regarding Challenge 2, promoting responsible consumption, the data could be used to monitor the impact of individual consumption on the immediate environment, to foster actions to promote more responsible consumption and to enable the public sharing of household consumption data. Finally, in the framework of monitoring biodiversity, the focus of Challenge 3, some attendees suggested that this data could be useful for designing policies to combat invasive species at municipal level.

Thematic group on Health

Question 1: What are the most important socio-environmental challenges in the field of health?

The participants in the Health group listed 6 challenges that they consider most important to address today in that field: Nutrition, diet, obesity; Sedentary lifestyles; Loneliness (particularly among elderly people); Mental health (particularly among adolescents); Noise pollution; and Air pollution.

Question 2: How can data sets generated through citizen science help to inform or improve public policies?

Generally speaking, the participants felt that citizen science could be a useful tool for involving and empowering patients at primary treatment and care units, with the ultimate goal of generating a change in behaviour, guiding citizens towards better health practices and more autonomous management, which would also give some respite to the pressure on health services.

At a more specific level, the participants focused on the useful intersection between health and the new technologies. From this perspective, data generated through citizen science could be used to validate technological tools that improve people's health, enabling patients to monitor their own health (for example, controlling their physical activity, food intake, food purchases and so on). This monitoring would help patients to follow the guidelines given to them by healthcare professionals to lead a healthier life. Citizen science could also serve to change the view of how citizens communicate with doctors (for example, by collecting photographs of what patients eat instead of talking to healthcare workers) as well as generating groups of patients and taking pressure off the care system. However, we should also remember that, according to the participants, this digitalisation process could also lead to problems of inclusion due to age, culture, or socio-economic problems, although the participants felt that, over the next few years, most of the population will be accustomed to and have access to this type of technology.

The participants stressed particularly the importance of data for improving prevention and early detection policies as well as increasing the impact of campaigns. Here, the debate focused not only on the need to generate new data and the challenge of crossing data generated by citizens with standardised data, but also on the idea of sharing data between different public spheres (such as data from the social system). The participants felt that a multidisciplinary approach is essential for addressing the health and management challenges of complex data sets, and that the new technologies and Artificial Intelligence can be effective tools for processing and sharing this data. However, they also note that care must be taken with regard to the openness of the data, as this is sensitive information that requires a high level of confidentiality.

Finally, it should be noted that the participants felt that efforts to include citizens in health processes and projects have been made for some time by different health organizations, but that effort to this end is not finding success: to promote a real paradigm shift it is necessary to implement specific actions and move into action.

Thematic group on Environmental Quality

Question 1: What are the most important socio-environmental challenges in the field of environmental quality?

The participants listed 4 main challenges: air quality, climate change, the circular economy and changing behaviours, consumption patterns and lifestyles.

Question 2: How can data sets generated through citizen science help to inform or improve public policies?

The participants in the environmental quality group reported the following:

- Inclusion in the co-creation of the administrations: it is necessary to work together with the administrations from the project definition stage on. Political commitment is needed to ensure that the results of the participatory process can really inform policies.
- A distinction should be made between citizen participation and citizen science.
- European projects and capitalisation projects (Interreg) can be a good tool for creating pilots and providing reassurance against fears of different health organizations.
- Organisation of intersectoral meetings/conferences/forums: it is important to work in cooperation with other stakeholders to create a common language. The pace at which different stakeholders operate is also different, but it is possible to begin working once such differences are accepted.
- Particular emphasis should be placed on the bonds between companies and citizens.
- There is talk of a paradigm shift in which all stakeholders should be involved.

Thematic group on Waste

Question 1: What are the most important socio-environmental challenges in the field of waste?

The participants pointed to four main challenges, which span the entire cycle, from product production to waste treatment: reducing waste generation; increasing selective collection; raising levels of responsible consumption; R&D: and developing more environmentally-friendly materials, services and processes.

General conclusions from the session

One of the main conclusions from the session is that the active cooperation of government, academia, companies and citizens is necessary to resolve socio-environmental challenges. This means creating frameworks and spaces for collaboration among quadruple helix stakeholders, since they cannot address the challenges and problems that affect them alone. Here, CS suggests approaches and methodologies to articulate this collaboration, aimed at addressing society's challenges, more effectively.

The participants also agreed on the **need to move into action**. Many manifestos and agreements have been established to promote responsible research and innovation that promote the inclusion of citizens and seek to involve them in designing public policies, which should focus on social needs. However, in the final outcome, neither research nor public policies include citizens in their processes.

Regarding the role that the different quadruple helix stakeholders should play in promoting citizen science as a tool to improve public policies, the participants noted the following:

Regarding the role that the government should play, the participants noted its capacity to promote cooperation among all quadruple helix stakeholders. Governments are charged with resolving societal challenges and have the tools and budget (though not unlimited) to do so.

Government has the capacity to include citizens in the design, implementation and monitoring of public policies and to promote and fund research and innovation projects that include citizens. Governments should also generate spaces for collaboration and networking among quadruple helix stakeholders and use its capacity to promote the collective action necessary to address the societal challenges.

As for the role of the **business sector**, the participants noted that the **involvement of companies is essential to address socio-environmental challenges**. It is vital for companies to contribute with their activities to resolving socio-environmental challenges. In other words, apart from economic value, they should also generate social and environmental value. Cooperation with citizens is key to developing new business models and new products and services that respond to changes in consumer preferences. Companies can also play a key role in developing technologies, platforms and tools to facilitate the generation, visualisation and interpretation of citizen-generated data. It is also vital to develop protocols to guarantee transparency, the protection of personal data and other ethical criteria.

Regarding the **academic world**, the participants highlighted its role in **applying methodological frameworks and designing protocols and projects** to guarantee the quality of processes and data. This scientific rigour is essential to ensure that citizen-generated data can be integrated into the policy-making cycle. Moreover, including citizen science in curricula and promoting courses and training in citizen science aimed at companies, administrations and citizens are other important actions required.

Citizen science cannot be conceived without the active involvement of **citizens**. Accordingly, it is essential for citizens to see how their involvement in science projects and in the design of public policies can generate benefits.

2.3 Webinars 3 and 4. How to begin co-designing a citizen science project to address a real socio-environmental challenge

Development of the session

The third and fourth webinars followed a practical approach. They were aimed at co-designing a CS project to address real socio-environmental challenges. Based on the interests shared by the participants, three challenges were proposed in the areas of water, health, and waste. For each challenge, a “challenge owner” was identified (public administration or company) who had to propose a real socio-environmental challenge to work on during each session.

Webinar 3	
1. Reminder of RRI and citizen science concepts	Review of the main concepts of RRI and citizen science in order to carry out the exercise.
2. Practical exercise Part I	<p>Activity 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the challenge characteristics • What do we know about the challenge? • What do we need to know? <p>Activity 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project objectives • How do we integrate the six dimensions of the RRI in the project? <p>Activity 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping agents to be involved in the project
Webinar 4	
3. Practical exercise Part II	<p>Division of participants into 3 groups -Water, Health and Waste-.</p> <p>Activity 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification of the scope of the CS project <p>Activity 2:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For each objective, identify the data that could provide the citizenry to achieve the project objectives ● Identify the data collection method <p>Activity 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify the citizen groups that should be involved ● Propose diverse strategies for citizen participation <p>Activity 4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Determine potential difficulties or problems to develop the project ● Propose strategies to overcome those challenges
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Table 5. Thematic structure of the third and fourth webinar

Main results

Thematic group on Water

Challenge owner: SUEZ-AGBAR company

CHALLENGE. Restoration of riparian forests and elimination of negative impacts.

Image 8. Project objectives and RRI dimensions

Objective 1. Monitoring the state of the riparian forest and its relationship with ecosystem services (including cultural services)

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unified and simplified methodology/protocol to measure the quality of the riparian forest: starting with the from the official protocol, "translate it" into a simple simple language. Validate with the public - Causes of degradation: different agents and different different sections of the river Incorporate data from already existing initiatives (observation of oceans, etc.) - Inventory of plant species - List of ecosystem services - Uses of land around forests - Uses by the public - Map of flows of pedestrians and vehicles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Field trips - Surveys
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizens in general (surrounding villages) - Citizen associations - Young public: Schools, youth associations - Corporate volunteering - Retired population (free time) - University students in natural sciences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities in local festivities and in dates (Water Day, Biodiversity Day, etc.). Biodiversity Day, etc.) - Excursions - Workshops - Established groups for the sponsorship of stretches of river

Table 6. Results objective 1

Objective 2. To make the data available to the public

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses and intensity of use - Data on the ecological status and state of the forest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ceilings on the river paths - Apps - Map (web) viewer - Communication channel with the local administration - Linking official and citizen data
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Associations - Volunteering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web open to the public - On-line work spaces for river stretches - Participatory sessions on the rivers - Link with other participatory processes - Webinars - Collaboration with libraries and municipalities

Table 7. Results objective 2

Objective 3. To construct a global strategic framework for the conservation of riparian forests with the participation of all stakeholders

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results of the diagnosis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizen action campaigns: small challenges - Sharing data = open data - Participatory data collection - Cooperative identification of the different agents - Shared agenda
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Table of actors at the basin level - Public administration: - County council, Catalan Water Agency, etc. - Businesses and industries - Universities and research centres - Cultural associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation groups - Round tables - Living labs - Volunteering courses - Initiatives from the city councils

Table 8. Results objective 3

Objective 4. To implement improvements to protect riparian forests according to a global vision and including all the stakeholders involved

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actions + evaluation + results + impact - Difficulties + successes - Priority actions & Budget 	
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public administration: ACA + municipal managers - Table of actors at county level (the same as above). - Schools - Gardening, landscape gardening and restoration institutes - Naturalist associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration in the curriculum or tasks of social services in schools - Same items of objective 1

Table 9. Results objective 4

Objective 5. Awareness-raising

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concerns of the public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Didactic materials - Surveys
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Schools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness-raising companies - Awareness-raising is an intrinsic component of the citizen science activities - Sponsoring actions

Table 10. Results objective 5

Potential difficulties & proposed strategies

FACTORS	DIFFICULTIES	MEASURES TO BE TAKEN
POLITICAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other political priorities Industry and the economy by the river 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involving political actors from the outset Citizen mobilisation

	<p>Reluctance to disclose certain data</p> <p>Very slow administrative processes</p> <p>Changes in government</p>	<p>Different departments and ministries involved</p>
ECONOMIC	<p>Polluting companies that generate employment</p> <p>Economic interests in the exploitation of the river</p> <p>Lack of budget for developing actions</p>	<p>Promotion of social innovation</p> <p>Participation in public calls for proposals</p> <p>Involve companies from the outset</p> <p>Knowing the lobbies and their interests</p> <p>Private sector as a funder</p> <p>Detect where the administration already considers that there is a problem</p>
SOCIAL	<p>Illegal appropriations</p> <p>Lack of time or interest = Low participation</p> <p>Lack of representativeness or social strength of the promoters</p> <p>Maintenance of interest</p>	<p>Expert facilitators</p> <p>Involvement of local councils, alternatives to illegal uses</p> <p>Identification of the most interested groups for each stage</p> <p>Giving feedback = generating a sense of relevance</p>
TECHNOLOGICAL	<p>Excluded population due to the methodology used.</p> <p>Technical resources, who is in charge?</p> <p>Obsolete or poorly integrable tools in the tools of the administration</p>	<p>Adaptation of the methodology to all citizenship</p> <p>Include an expert technological expert technologist</p> <p>Include gamification</p> <p>Open software</p>
FUNCTIONALITY / USABILITY / PROCESS	<p>Unrepresentative data</p> <p>Doubts on validity</p>	<p>Establish validation protocols</p> <p>Different channels of information = avoiding barriers</p> <p>Involve the working group in the validation</p> <p>Periodic training</p>

Table 11. Results difficulties & strategies

Thematic group on Health

CHALLENGE OWNER: Hospital Sant Pau

CHALLENGE: Invisibility, underdiagnosis and lack of research into specific women’s diseases: the case of endometriosis

Image 9. Project objectives and RRI dimensions

Objective 1: To empower women in their knowledge of endometriosis and the diagnostic process

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Degree of knowledge about the disease - Perception of pain - Knowledge about the associative & support network - Experiences and feelings of women who suffer endometriosis - Data on normality/abnormality in menstruation - Level of incidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surveys, interviews, focus groups - Dialogues between women and experts - Apps - Working groups - Pain scale
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<p>Public administration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary health care and other specific services and information services - Adult schools <p>Citizenship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reading spaces and entities (women) - Institutes and spaces for young people - Neighbourhood centres - Meeting places for women from different backgrounds - Women's and feminist associations - Parent associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informative sessions - Agenda of activities - Workshops - Playful information activities - Surveys

Table 11. Results objective 1

Objective 2. To train health, social service and educational workers in the field of endometriosis

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women's experience in the health and social services, barriers = detecting needs for training for professionals - Demands and concerns of patients - Knowledge of the disease by the professionals, symptoms, diagnosis and alternatives - Impact on working life - Action protocols - Data on the use of medication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer information to pharmacies and primary health care centres + - Identify cases - Consultation with health and social services - Learning communities - Workshops between experts and patients - Surveys with key questions (to women and professionals) - Informative workshops - Focus groups - Comparison of diagnoses between populations
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<p>Company and Academia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers at schools and institutes - Pharmacies - Women's psychologists - Child psychologists <p>Public administration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gynecologists in sexual and reproductive health care units - Health personnel in Primary health care - Catalan Society of Obstetrics and Gynaecology - Citizenship - Young people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Youth Evening in sexual and reproductive health care units - Parents' meeting places - Informative sessions and workshops - Information material - Spaces for open dialogue with professionals - Emails to members

Table 12. Results objective 2

Objective 3. To increase research on endometriosis

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elements that could be linked to the disease - Resource mobilisation - Treatment of symptoms - New lines of research - Validated survey = detection of risk factors - "State of the art" gender-mental health - Number of clinical studies in progress, publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Form available to professionals = generating robust datasets linked to other types of data - Partnership linked to the industrial and pharmaceutical sector - Creation of funding opportunities - Living labs = generate links between industry, civil society and professionals - Create a multidisciplinary group
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<p>Company and academia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funders - CataloniaBIO, HEALTHTECH, ICD - Universities (young researchers, research groups) <p>Public administration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary health care = research structure IDIAP-GOL - Catalan Women's Institute / ICS / GENCAT <p>Citizenship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women with the disease - Grassroots women's associations - Neighbourhood Associations, Parent - Teacher Associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meetings, lobbying - Information sessions - Focus groups = prioritising research objectives - Workshops in the faculties/universities - Bilateral training for prevention = patients' associations + professionals + women's associations - A dynamising agent who identifies groups and creates a multidisciplinary team - Publicity campaigns

Table 13. Results objective 3

Objective 4. To raise-awareness and promote multi-level awareness on endometriosis among women, citizens, industry

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data collection among women - Degree of knowledge of the teachers who teach in health and sexual health, citizenship, professionals, etc. = to demonstrate the lack of coneixement - Level of knowledge on the part of men = to detect stereotypes - Spreading awareness of the disease among teenage girls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surveys of teachers and parents' associations - Community of champions to carry out the interviews - On-the-street + telephone surveys - School workshops - Discussion groups in civic centres - Campaigns with infographics - Testimonies in public spaces - Museum - Interviews with teachers - Taking into account the social diversity of the neighbourhoods - Structures of the neighbourhood to raise awareness=libraries, pharmacies, civil houses
WHICH GROUPS OF CITIZENS?	STRATEGIES?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World of culture, festivals - Media for young people, influencers - Primary health care and Family Planning Centres - Prevention programme for young girls = early detection - Schools, universities - Libraries, gymnasiums - Don't forget men as a target public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report - Giving information and asking for diffusion - Information sessions + awareness campaigns - TV3 Marathon - Information leaflets, posters - Explain the project

Table 14. Results objective 4

Potential difficulties & proposed strategies

FACTORS	DIFFICULTIES	MEASURES TO BE TAKEN
POLITICAL	Current priority COVID Limited capacity of influence Lack of aggregated data to exert pressure Electoral period Lack of importance of women's groups in lobbies Difficulty to work in a coordinated manner Decision-making bodies mostly represented by men Economic and social crisis	Good organisation of actors Studies on women's issues Defining a shared agenda Raising awareness of decision-makers Social pressure = type of "me too" campaign
ECONOMIC	Lack of research funding COVID crisis Lack of interest on the part of the companies = investment in women's products	Alternative ways of financing Economic impact report Making it visible that this is an business opportunity Making the existence and impact visible EU funds for women's issues
SOCIAL	Social and family burden Taboo around female sexuality Patriarchy - gender violence Ignorance of the disease Low awareness Difficulty in reaching certain groups of women	Visibilising / naturalising female sexuality Dissemination campaigns Make investment in endometriosis attractive Give importance to invisibilization as gender violence
TECHNOLOGICAL	Distrust about the use of data Digital fracture of certain groups	Search for non-technological measures Different ways of diffusion
FUNCTIONALITY / USABILITY / PROCESS	Lack of participation Apps used = problems of inclusivity	Adapt the tools to realities Caring for, giving feedback to the people involved
OTHER	Lack of leadership resources Competition vs. Collaboration Fragmentation and mistrust of leadership	Find funding to develop projects Include professionals in a transversal way throughout the project To build a lobby "women's health".

Table 15. Results difficulties & strategies

CHALLENGE OWNER: Mollet del Vallès municipality

CHALLENGE: To increase and improve waste separation at source

Image 10. Project objectives and RRI dimensions

Objective 1. To provide information to the public on the waste management system

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actual procedure of waste - Costs and revenues of the system. Data per fractions - Carbon footprint - Cost (economic, environmental) of the purchased products - Tracking of waste: so that people can know when a waste arrives at the plant (code) - Which products do not have a recycling alternative? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information translated in an easy way: idea of a ranking - Individualised information - Interactive games (gamification) - Social return of waste campaign: counters - Apps

Table 16. Results objective 1

Objective 2. To establish a system of environmental taxation or incentives (individual or collective)

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentives to motivate people - Individualised data on the generation and use of waste collection elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Channelling participatory taxes - Interviews with people who do not recycle. They can be carried out by the citizenship - Identify levers for change - Conduct a sociological study - Take into account all groups of citizens - Open debates

Table 17. Results objective 2

Objective 3. To make extended producer responsibility effective

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blockchain: traceability - Impact of each product 	<p>None</p>

Table 18. Results objective 3

Objective 4. To co-design, with citizens, an innovative selective waste collection system suitable for different circumstances and stakeholders

WHAT DATA?	HOW?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The data generated can be used for the design of selective waste collection pilots, as well as for their monitoring once implemented in order to correct or add improvements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working groups - Surveys at street level (NGOs, neighbourhood associations...)

Table 19. Results objective 4

General conclusions from the sessions

The work completed in sessions 3 and 4 reveal the large number of variables, issues and perspectives that should be taken into account when co-designing a citizen science project. The participants became aware of the importance of how challenges and associated research questions are established. The participation in a co-design process of the entities that propose challenges and seek to resolve them is key for a better understanding of limitations and conditioning factors and to ensure that the project actually responds to the needs identified. The construction of citizen science projects is complex and requires the cooperation and engagement of different types of stakeholders and the support of experts in citizen science.

Sessions 3 and 4 made it possible to propose three possible pilot projects to the TRANSFORM project, on the following themes:

- Municipal waste management;
- The problem of invisibility, underdiagnosis and lack of research into diseases that prevalently or specifically affect women (i.e. endometriosis);
- The restoration of riparian forests and the elimination of negative impacts on river basins.

3. The co-design of pilot projects

3.1 Selection criteria within the RIS3CAT framework

RIS3CAT is conceived as a research and innovation-driven agenda for economic transformation. RIS3CAT identifies the three vectors that should guide the transformation of the Catalan economy: industrial tradition, quality of life, and the green economy. Smart specialisation is understood as an open, progressive process of specialization: through the process of co-design, stakeholders in the Catalan research and innovation system define the subareas of specialisation in which Catalonia has competitive advantages and is well positioned in Europe. This approach is aligned with that of the European Commission, according to which RIS3 strategies should not select sectors, but should support the development of bottom-up initiatives by players in the research and innovation ecosystem, often at subsector or intersectoral level.

Under RIS3CAT, the public administration is called on to play a key role as a driver of innovation and social transformation through policies aimed at mobilising knowledge and capacities in the territory to generate new responses to societal challenges. In 2019, a line of action was launched aimed at introducing the RRI approach and transformative innovation policy into RIS3CAT. The Horizon 2020 projects [SeeRRI](#) and TRANSFORM provide spaces to explore and test ways of integrating the RRI approach into the RIS3CAT.

GENCAT's activities in TRANSFORM focuses on finding answers to the following three important questions:

- How CS can provide new evidence and perspectives and, through this, contribute to a better understanding and management of transformative change and transition towards more sustainable and inclusive development pathways.
- How CS can provide new evidence and perspectives and, through this, contribute to more effective public policies and actions, by uncovering the blind spots in current public policies and actions that lead to an inability to change the pathway or to unintentional side effects.

- How CS can contribute to articulating new forms of collaboration among academia, public administrations, companies and civil society to address the challenges that matter to society more effectively.

Within this framework, the criteria that the 2 pilot projects must fulfil are the following (see TRANSFORM milestone 12):

- The projects focus on challenges that can be addressed through CS.
- The projects address a societal challenge and at least one Sustainable Development Goal (therefore, they are relevant for other territories).
- The projects are connected to the RIS3CAT priorities and instruments.
- There are relevant Catalan institutions willing to act as “challenge owners” and to guarantee an impact beyond TRANSFORM.
- The projects are relevant for 4H stakeholders in the Catalan research and innovation ecosystem and for public policies, providing answers to the three former questions
- It is feasible to co-design and implement the projects in the 2021-2022 period, generating results that can be measured and that are relevant for TRANSFORM and RIS3CAT.
- In combination, the projects address environmental and social issues, including gender equality.

As described in Section 2, one of the results from the four Think Tank webinars was the identification of three potential CS pilot projects that were relevant for quadruple helix stakeholders:

- Municipal waste management.
- The problem of invisibility, underdiagnosis and lack of research into women’s diseases, specifically endometriosis.
- Restoration of riparian forests and elimination of negative impacts on river basins.

Municipal waste management is a very important issue for both RIS3CAT and the Catalan Waste Agency, which participates in the Think Tank. There are many initiatives by local authorities in this field, and most of the municipalities participating in the Think Tank were interested in involving citizens in the co-design of innovative waste collection systems.

The Catalan Cluster selected Mollet local authority for the pilot project, since this municipality is participating in a RIS3CAT zero-waste initiative (shared agenda B-30) in cooperation with the Universitat Autònoma of Barcelona (Autonomous University of Barcelona). The collaboration of the municipality with the university was also a relevant factor in selecting this territory, since this

collaboration opened up opportunities to engage students in the pilot project. From the beginning, Mollet City Council local authorities and Universitat Autònoma of Barcelona expressed their interest in collaborating with TRANSFORM and in enhancing synergies between TRANSFORM and the RIS3CAT territorial project.

RIS3CAT is highly specialised in the health sector. However, there are many initiatives, but none focuses on women. Gender equality is a very relevant issue in health policies. Sant Pau Hospital and the Catalan Agency for Health Quality and Evaluation (AQuAS) participated in the 4 webinars and were from the first moment very interested in developing this project.

The restoration of forests is also a very relevant issue, but the interest expressed by the participants in the Think Tank was not as great as in the other two cases and for this reason it was not selected.

For both pilots, from January to March 2021, more than 20 meetings were held with the Catalan Cluster and the organisations involved to define common needs, pilot objectives, stakeholders to engage and engagement strategies. In January 2021, a work plan proposal was drawn up and agreed by all the organisations involved.

3.2 Pilot project on women's health

As described in Section 2, the project on endometriosis was the result of co-creation exercises generated by the Think Tank sessions.

The challenge owners of this project are Sant Pau Hospital and the Catalan Agency for Health Quality and Evaluation (AQuAS). In it, they address the issue of the “invisibility, underdiagnosis and lack of research to specific diseases affecting women: the case of endometriosis.”

The title of the pilot is “L’Endometriosi en primera persona: recerca participativa sobre vivències, valoracions i necessitats de les persones amb endometriosi” (“Endometriosis in the first person: participatory research into the experiences, assessments and needs of people with endometriosis”).

The project objectives are:

- 1) To collect first-person experiences of people with endometriosis, specifically, the process experienced from the first symptoms to diagnosis.
- 2) To collect assessments and needs regarding services and resources in relation to the diagnosis, care and support of people with endometriosis.

The project was co-designed by Sant Pau Hospital and AQuAS in two phases:

Phase 1. Creation of a diverse group of people affected by endometriosis to collect their first-person accounts of the experience of this disorder, the process experienced from the first symptoms to the medical diagnosis; also, their assessments and needs regarding existing diagnosis, care and support services and resources. In order to involve a larger number of people, the information obtained from the group will be enriched by information from a wider group of those affected. Through structured dialogues, information will be collected in order to draft a report containing recommendations for policy makers and health personnel aimed at improving service and resources for the diagnosis, care and support of endometriosis.

Phase 2. In the second phase, the most relevant variables and indicators for the people affected (such as psychosocial aspects, aspects of care, needs, taboos, stigma, etc.) that can be used to create a digital tool to support self-assessment and early detection of endometriosis will be identified and validated. In accordance with the principles of citizen science, we seek to place first-person experience and the

experiences of other stakeholders in the field of health research and management on an equal footing. Consequently, this tool will be co-created with the affected people themselves and other relevant stakeholders (healthcare workers, researchers, etc.). Under TRANSFORM, the tool will be developed up to the pre-test stage (without data analysis).

3.3 Pilot project in waste management

As described in Section 2, the project on waste management was a result of the co-creation exercises that took place at the Think Tank sessions.

The challenge owner of this project is Mollet del Vallès local authority, with the support of Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Barcelona Autonomous University). The challenge they are working on is “Increasing and improving waste separation at source”

The project title is “Citizen science per al disseny i implementació d’un ‘joc interactiu dels residus’ que contribueixi a millorar la recollida selectiva de residus municipals” (“Citizen science for the design and implementation of an ‘interactive waste game’ to contribute to the selective collection of municipal waste”).

The project objectives are:

- 1) To open up to the public the current debates on the implementation of different innovative selective collection systems.
- 2) To generate an active awareness of the environmental impact of waste, helping to promote co-responsibility.
- 3) To compile behaviours, attitudes, ideas, and preferences and identify barriers and needs for the implementation of new waste collection systems.

The project was co-designed with Mollet local authority. It consists of two phases:

Phase 1. This first phase of the pilot will consist of the **co-creation of a tool (interactive waste game)**. The development of the tool will involve the challenge owner, Mollet local authority, and a diverse group of citizens. It will also count with the support of students and staff members of the Autonomous University of Barcelona. The co-creation process will take into account several variables for the co-design of innovative urban waste collection systems (including technical, social and economic variables). Once this process is over, the game will be produced for its implementation.

Phase 2. The second phase will involve the application of this game as a citizen science tool. The tool will be tested at several schools and other civic infrastructures in the municipality over a period of two months. The game is intended to:

- a) raise awareness about the impacts of waste;
- b) collect data on citizens' behaviours, attitudes, habits, perceptions;
- c) identify barriers to the implementation of innovative waste collection systems;
- d) select the most suitable innovative waste collection systems for the various neighbourhoods in Mollet del Vallès, where different socio-economic, urban and demographic contexts are present.

This game is expected to be used by a wide range of municipalities also beyond TRANSFORM project, as many municipalities have shown their interest in replicating this approach to inform their own waste management processes.

4. Next steps

The pilot projects, which will be implemented in 2021 and 2022, will contribute to generating new evidence and knowledge about CS in relation to citizen engagement and transformative public policies, i.e. policies that address the SDGs.

In this initial period, the main activities of the Catalan Cluster focused on the process of co-creation of the two pilot projects. The first phase of this regional co-creation process was highly participative, involving the members of the TRANSFORM Think Tank. The process led to the co-design and selection of two pilot projects: a pilot project on women's health, with the participation of the Sant Pau Hospital and the Catalan Agency for Health Quality and Evaluation (AQuAS), both as challenge owners; and a pilot scheme focusing on waste management, with the participation of Mollet del Vallès local authority as challenge owner and the support of Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Both pilot projects are being co-created in cooperation with stakeholders in the territory.

The Catalan Cluster is also working on the theory of change for the two pilot projects and the monitoring methodology in order to collect learnings and evidence from the two projects and to generate new knowledge that can be relevant for science and public policies and, particularly, for smart specialisation strategies in Catalonia.

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